

CLASSIFICATIONS OF LOAN WORDS IN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: This thesis discusses the classifications of loan words in linguistics and provides a structural analysis.

Keywords: loan words, language, linguistics, loan-shift, translation.

In studying the origin and history of loan words, the researcher finds that Linguist like and Greavu (2017) has organized four types of loan words based on Haugen's classification in (1950) as the following:

(1) Loanword: it's an adopt item uses for both donor language and reception language and undergoes different grammatical procedures.

(2) Loan-shift: it's another procedure adapting native terms to conform new shifting meanings.

(3) Loan-translation: A Calque or Loan-translation takes place when the native word is taken from another language but partly or fully translated like the German word (*lehnwort*), the French phrase (marriage of convenience), etc.

(4) Loan-blend: it's a word that one of its element is loan and the other is native such as the loanword *preost* (priest) comes with the native element *-had to mean* (hood) in old English to provide new word (preosthad = priesthood).

However, MaLaughlin (2017) referred to another classification of loanwords focused on the degree of modification into the native or recipient language. This classification is best known as Haugen's classifications¹:

a) Non adapted loanwords keep their authentic written form as well as the pronunciation reflects the authentic one (*ex: road*).

b) Compound loanwords and quotation loanwords are another group of non-adapted borrowings (*ex: interview, and last minute*).

c) Partially adapted loanwords tend to adopt terms or words in a way that likes or resembles in forms the native words, *ex: English loanwords in the Czech language (ex: hockey → hokej)*.

d) Completely adapted loanwords are set of word-forming elements of the donor language with elements of the recipient language, *ex: English loanwords in the Czech language (calendar → kalendář)*.

¹ Greavu, A. (2017). A Classification of Borrowings: Observations from Romanian/English Contact. *Diversité et Identité Culturelle En Europe*.

e) Classification according to the way we pronounce the abbreviations, which divided to:

Abbreviations uttered as words according to the letters or graphemes which spelled as one word and never spelled separately, such as: (NASA, NATO, AIDS, and MASH).

2. Abbreviations uttered as a set of letters, such as: (CV, DVD, OK, and PC).

However, at the end of loan word classification, the researcher finds that the term loan word was first emerged in the year (1950) by the Linguist Haugen followed by others through history. But yet, the term still as it was since (1950) till nowadays never change or even modified. These things show the importance of loan words as an eternal term never lost its importance in studying language from the past till now, and the studies on this field never stop or are out of date. (See Diagram 1)

Diagram 2: Haugen's Classification of Loan Words

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